

MOISTURE PENETRATION INTO COMPOSITES UNDER EXTERNAL STRESSES: A SCALE TRANSITION ANALYSIS

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SUMMARY

A multi-scale approach coupling the internal mechanical states localised within the plies constituents to the Fick's law governing the moisture diffusion process was used for modelling the response of composite laminates submitted to environmental hygroscopic loads, from the transient part of the diffusion process to its permanent stage.

Keywords: moisture diffusion, internal stresses, hygromechanical coupling, multi-scale modeling.

INTRODUCTION

High performance organic matrix composites are being increasingly used in aerospace and marine structural applications. They are often submitted to moisture which can lead to composite degradation and loss of mechanical properties [1-3]. Efforts have been made to study the effects of moisture, and develop analytical models for predicting the multi-scale mechanical states occurring during the moisture diffusion process in fiber-reinforced laminates [4-7]. In these works, the moisture transport was assumed to follow the classical Fickian model. Nevertheless, valuable experimental results [8] have shown that certain anomalies in the moisture sorption process, (i.e. discrepancies from the expected Fickian behaviour) could be explained by a coupling between the moisture transport in polymers and the local stress state [9]. It has been claimed that a mechanical loading enhances the moisture-penetration mechanisms producing higher diffusion coefficients and maximum levels of moisture penetration.

In the present study, a scale transition analysis is achieved in order to investigate the coupled effect of the internal mechanical states, experienced by epoxy resin composite structures, on the moisture penetration process. The hygro-mechanical model accounts for the proper evolution of the water diffusion behaviour parameters (diffusion coefficients and maximum moisture contents) of the epoxy resin constituting each ply of the composite structure, during the transient part of the diffusion process. The scale transition approach provides relations linking the plies stresses (strains) to those of the constituents (epoxy and reinforcements) and homogenization procedures enabling to estimate the evolution of the plies diffusion behaviour law, from that of the epoxy, at any step of the moisture diffusion. The effects induced by typical laminates lay-up configurations are investigated. The numerical results, obtained according to the hygro-mechanical coupled model are also compared to the traditional uncoupled model.

ACCOUNTING FOR A COUPLING BETWEEN THE MECHANICAL STATES AND THE MOISTURE DIFFUSION IN PURE ORGANIC MATRIX

Polymer constitutes the preferential penetration path for small molecules, such as water, diffusing through organic matrix composites. Transport phenomena in polymers are generally explained by theories based on the free volume notion [10-11]. Free volume actually corresponds to the difference between the specific (macroscopic) volume of the polymer and the actual volume occupied by its constitutive molecules.

Moreover, the heterogeneous swelling, which accompanies sorption or desorption of water, yields a multi-scale stress pattern in a composite structure. This aspect has been the subject of numerous papers over the past few years [2-3, 12]. It was suggested that the swelling stresses in polymer membranes, through which a penetrant diffuses, affects the diffusion coefficient [13-14]. Due to the heterogeneous moisture diffusion behaviour of the epoxy resins, on the one hand, and that of the carbon fibers, on the other hand, the hygro-mechanical coupling occurring in composite structures initiates at the scale of the constituents. Thus, the purpose of this work obviously requires a multi-scale approach. However, multi-scale model implies the knowledge of the specific behaviour of the elementary constituents of the representative elementary volume. Thus, the following paragraphs will be devoted to the study of the hygro-mechanical coupling existing in the pure matrix, which affects both parameters governing the Fickian diffusion law: i) the diffusion coefficient, and ii) the maximum moisture absorption capacity.

Moisture Diffusion Coefficient

Historically, a theoretical approach based on the calculation of the free-volume change in the stressed state [16] was developed. In practice, it was later observed that the main mechanical state controlling the hygro-mechanical coupling was the strain instead of the stresses [16-17]: assuming that the Fickian diffusion coefficient was related to the free volume by the Doolittle equation, the authors proposed an expression for the ratio of the diffusion coefficients in the strained and free-of-strain states:

$$\text{Ln} \left(\frac{D_{\varepsilon}^m}{D_0^m} \right) = \frac{a}{v^m} \left(\frac{1}{v_{f0}^m} - \frac{1}{v_{f\varepsilon}^m} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where D_0^m and D_{ε}^m are the Fickian moisture diffusion coefficients for the strain-free matrix and that of the strained epoxy, respectively, whereas a is an empirical factor. According to experimental results on pure epoxies [17], a varies in a narrow range: $0.031 \leq a \leq 0.036$. v^m denotes the volume fraction of the matrix in the composite ply, v_{f0}^m and $v_{f\varepsilon}^m$ are the free volume fraction of the strain-free and strained epoxy matrix, respectively. Many authors agree that v_{f0}^m tends towards 2.5% [15, 16] in a defect-free resin. The free-volume fraction for a strained epoxy is related to its counterpart existing in the corresponding unstrained resin through:

$$v_{f\varepsilon}^m = v_{f0}^m + \frac{\Delta V^m}{V_0^m} = v_{f0}^m + \frac{V_{\varepsilon}^m - V_0^m}{V_0^m} = v_{f0}^m + \text{Tr } \varepsilon^m \quad (2)$$

Where $\frac{\Delta V^m}{V_0^m}$ stands for the organic matrix volume variation induced by the strains, this ratio being equal to the trace of the strain tensor experienced by the polymer matrix $\text{Tr } \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^m$. V_ε^m and V_0^m denote the volume of the strained and unstrained organic matrix, respectively.

Equations (1) and (2) yield the following expression for the Fickian moisture diffusion coefficients of the strained/unstrained resins:

$$\text{Ln} \left(\frac{D_\varepsilon^m}{D_0^m} \right) = \frac{a}{v^m} \frac{\Delta V^m}{V_0^m} \left\{ v_{f0}^m \left[v_{f0}^m + \frac{\Delta V^m}{V_0^m} \right] \right\}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

In order to estimate the diffusion coefficient of the strained matrix D_ε^m , the knowledge of both the organic matrix strains and its strain-free diffusion coefficient D_0^m is required. D_0^m can be deduced from the slope of the mass uptake evolution as a function of the time power $1/2$, when the time tends towards 0 (thus, at the beginning of the diffusion process). For a N5208 epoxy, this coefficient, measured at room temperature is: $D_0^m = 13,484 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. According to (3), D_ε^m increases when the trace of the polymer strains is positive, and decreases when this trace is negative. This is consistent with the practical observations: the diffusion coefficient of a pure epoxy increases when it is submitted to an uniaxial tension, whereas it decreases when submitted to an uniaxial compression [15]. The same authors state, that the increased water uptake induced by a tensile load depends not only on the diffusion coefficient but also on the equilibrium water concentration and that the stress state may indeed influence both these parameters. This second feature will be developed in the next paragraph.

Maximum Moisture Absorption Capacity

The maximum moisture absorption capacity $M_{\infty 0}^m$ for an unstrained epoxy is defined for instance in [16]. Let us assume that the maximum moisture absorption capacity $M_{\infty \varepsilon}^m$ of the same organic matrix experiencing a strain state writes:

$$M_{\infty 0}^m = v_{f0}^m \times \frac{\rho^w}{\rho^m}; \quad M_{\infty \varepsilon}^m = v_{f\varepsilon}^m \times \frac{\rho^w}{\rho^m} \quad (4)$$

Combining equations (4) to relation (2) yields:

$$M_{\infty \varepsilon}^m = M_{\infty 0}^m + \left(v_{f\varepsilon}^m - v_{f0}^m \right) \times \frac{\rho^w}{\rho^m} = M_{\infty 0}^m + \frac{\Delta V^m}{V_0^m} \times \frac{\rho^w}{\rho^m} \quad (5)$$

COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Modelling The Moisture Diffusion Process

Consider a laminated hollow cylinder, whose inner and outer radii are respectively $a = 1000$ mm and $b = 1004$ mm, composed of n plies delimited by cylinders with radii r_i and r_{i+1} . To solve Fick's equation, the boundary moisture contents have to be known. The moisture content at saturation is determined from the moisture content of the matrix (5). The mixed law on the volumes reads:

$$V^I = v^f \times V^f + v^m \times V^m \quad (6)$$

Where V^I , V^f and V^m are, respectively, the volumes of composite, fibers and matrix. v^f is the fibers volume fraction. Equation (6) can be expressed by introducing the moisture contents, and simplified, since the fibers do not absorb water:

$$\rho^I \times M_{\infty \varepsilon}^I = v^f \times \rho^f \times M_{\infty \varepsilon}^f + v^m \times \rho^m \times M_{\infty \varepsilon}^m \Rightarrow M_{\infty \varepsilon}^I = v^m \frac{\rho^m}{\rho^I} M_{\infty \varepsilon}^m \quad (7)$$

Where ρ^I , ρ^f and ρ^m are, respectively, the densities of the composite, fibers and matrix. The macroscopic moisture content (at ply scale) is a solution of Fick's equation with a moisture diffusion coefficient dependent on the matrix one, which is dependent on the local mechanical state. The expression of the effective moisture diffusion coefficient as a function of the moisture diffusion coefficient of the matrix is [18]:

$$D_{\varepsilon}^I = D_{\varepsilon}^m \frac{1 - v^f}{1 + v^f} \quad (8)$$

The moisture diffusion coefficient of the matrix is determined through (3) from the local strains deduced from the localization of the macroscopic strains. The hygromechanical coupling induces for the constitutive plies different moisture diffusion coefficients and moisture contents. Thus, the moisture flux is continuous at the interply and the moisture content is discontinuous [5]. The Fickian problem (9-10) can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} = D_i(t) \left[\frac{\partial^2 C_i}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial r} \right] \quad a < r < b, t > 0, i=1 \text{ to } n \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{cases} C_i(r_i, t) = \alpha_{i+1} C_{i+1}(r_i, t) \\ D_i(t) \frac{\partial C_i(r_i, t)}{\partial r} = D_{i+1}(t) \frac{\partial C_{i+1}(r_i, t)}{\partial r} \\ C(a, t) = M_{\infty}^a(t) \text{ and } C(b, t) = M_{\infty}^b(t) \\ C(r, 0) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$C_i(r, t)$ is the moisture content, $D_i(t)$ and $D_{i+1}(t)$ are the diffusion coefficients of two adjacent plies, α_{i+1} is the moisture content gap between two adjacent plies: $\alpha_{i+1} = \frac{(M_{\infty\varepsilon}^I)_{i+1}}{(M_{\infty\varepsilon}^I)_i}$; $(M_{\infty\varepsilon}^I)_{i+1}$ and $(M_{\infty\varepsilon}^I)_i$ being the maximum moisture

absorption capacity of the plies. $M_{\infty}^a(t)$ and $M_{\infty}^b(t)$ are the boundary moisture contents. This problem is solved by using the finite differences with an explicit scheme.

Mechanical Modelling

The macroscopic internal stresses are calculated through the homogenized properties and the classical equations of solid mechanics: constitutive laws of hygro-elastic orthotropic materials, strain-displacement relationship, boundary conditions, compatibility and equilibrium equations. The coupling between moisture diffusion and mechanical states involves an incremental resolution. The moisture dependant behaviour, between times t_{i-1} and t_i , can be expressed as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i^I - \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{i-1}^I = \bar{\mathbf{L}}^I : \left[(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^I - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{i-1}^I) - \bar{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^I (C_i^I - C_{i-1}^I) \right] \quad (11)$$

Where $\bar{\mathbf{L}}^I$ is the average macroscopic stiffness between t_{i-1} and t_i , $\bar{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^I$ the hygroscopic expansion and C the moisture content. The resulting local stresses in the constituents (fibers and matrix) are deduced from Eshelby-Kröner hygro-mechanical scale transition model. Since the fibers are impermeable, the local stresses-strains relation in the reinforcements and the scale transition strain localization respectively write:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^f = \mathbf{L}^f : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f; \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f = \left(\mathbf{L}^f + \mathbf{L}^I : \mathbf{R}^I \right)^{-1} : \left(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^I + \mathbf{L}^I : \mathbf{R}^I : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^I \right) \quad (12)$$

The local mechanical states in the epoxy matrix are provided by Hill's strains and stresses average laws [19]:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^m = \frac{1}{v^m} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^I - \frac{v^f}{v^m} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f; \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}^m = \frac{1}{v^m} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^I - \frac{v^f}{v^m} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^f \quad (13)$$

At every step of the calculation, the moisture diffusion coefficients are estimated through the knowledge of the preceding step multi-scale internal mechanical state, and especially from the volume strain of the ply organic matrix.

Numerical Results

The hygro-mechanical coupled model involves a time-dependent evolution of the boundary conditions in terms of moisture content. As a consequence, the predicted results should be closely dependent from the macroscopic maximum moisture absorption capacity M_0^I of the strains-free ply used for initialising the iterative calculation. Now, this parameter cannot be directly measured. Actually, at the beginning of the moisture diffusion, only an infinitely thin layer from the structure contains water.

Thus, the in-depth distribution of the moisture content presents important gradients (this effect clearly appears on Figure 2). For both these reasons, gravimetric measurements would not be easily achieved (because the mass variation would be weak in the explored specimen) neither be representative of M_0^I (because of the moisture content gradients). Nevertheless, at the permanent state of the diffusion process, in an unidirectional composite, kept in air saturated with water (100% relative humidity), containing 60% fiber volume fraction being, the measured moisture content tends towards 1,5%. A calculation method was dedicated to the finding of the initial maximum moisture absorption capacity M_0^I satisfying the condition, observed in practice $M_\infty^I = 1,5\%$ in the permanent state. This value was identified to be as low as $M_0^I = 0,73$ for an unidirectional ply initially dry, with $v^f = 60\%$. This parameter is valid for the coupled approach. In the case that the traditional uncoupled model is considered, the maximum moisture absorption capacity does not vary throughout the diffusion process. Thus, the aimed final value $M_\infty^I = 1,5\%$ corresponds to the initial value $M_0^I = 1,5\%$, as well.

The macroscopic maximum moisture content profiles obtained in the case of 4 mm thick thin tubular composites structures submitted to a purely hygroscopic load are presented on Figure 1. Two geometrical arrangements of the composite plies were considered: i) a $[+55^\circ/-55^\circ]$ laminate, and ii) an uni-directionally reinforced epoxy. Two sets of curves are displayed on Figure 1: the results obtained according to the coupled model are compared the predictions of the uncoupled model. According to Figure 1, the coupled hygro-mechanical model satisfies the condition that the maximum moisture absorption capacity reaches the threshold $M_\infty^I = 1,5\%$ in the unidirectional structure. In the case that the $\pm 55^\circ$ laminate is considered, the permanent state is attained for a maximum moisture absorption capacity limited to $M_\infty^I = 1,37\%$ only. This is actually due to a discrepancy between the mechanical strain states experienced by the two considered structures: the absolute value of $\text{Tr } \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^I$ is weaker in the laminate than in the unidirectional composite. This illustrates the contribution, made by the coupled model, by comparison to the more classical uncoupled approach. The uncoupled model is not capable to account for any change in the maximum absorption moisture capacity as a function of the time and space, during the transient part of the diffusion, neither it has the capability to account for an evolution of this parameter as a function of the very arrangement of the composite plies in a laminated structure.

The geometrical stacking of the composite plies, since it enables to optimize the multi-scale mechanical states experienced by the composite structure, should also enable to significantly optimize the parameters of the moisture diffusion process, such as the maximum moisture absorption capacity, or the moisture diffusion coefficient, so that the time and depth dependent moisture content profiles would be significantly altered, also. Contrary to the uncoupled model, the coupled hygro-mechanical model predicts stair-step shaped discontinuities of the in-depth maximum moisture absorption capacity evolutions. The discontinuities are actually located at the boundaries between the laminate layers, which are considered to experience an homogeneous local mechanical state at the scale of the plies constituents. They come from this very distribution of the multi-scale mechanical states, and especially from that of the organic matrix, because the hygro-mechanical coupling initiates at microscopic scale. This last assertion is compatible with the absence of discontinuities occurring at the beginning of the

moisture diffusion process and when the permanent state is reached, both these situations corresponding to particular cases, when the matrix strain is identical in each ply of the tubular structure.

Analogous effects do occur for the time and space dependent evolution of the macroscopic moisture diffusion coefficient, (which are thus, for obvious reasons, not displayed).

Figure 1: Comparison between the time and space dependent macroscopic permanent moisture absorption capacity profiles predicted by the coupled and uncoupled hygro-mechanical model in the (a) $\pm 55^\circ$ composite / (b) unidirectional composite structure.

Figure 2: Time and space dependent moisture content profiles in the (a) $\pm 55^\circ$ composite structure / (b) unidirectional composite structure of Coupled/Un-coupled Model.

Figure 2 displays the various in-depth time dependent evolutions of the moisture content in the studied hollow thin cylinders, calculated through both the coupled/uncoupled hygro-mechanical approaches. The coupled hygro-mechanical model predicts a strong evolution of the moisture content at the boundaries of the tube (within the structure itself, obviously), during the whole diffusion process, even though the applied external purely hygroscopic load is kept constant. This phenomenon, that does not occur in the case that the simulation are achieved according to the traditional uncoupled model, should be attributed to the variation, previously reported on Figure 1, of the maximum moisture absorption capacity, within the coupled framework.

Predicted Multi-scale Mechanical States

Figure 3 shows the multi-scale transverse stresses evolution in the internal ply of a) the laminated b) the unidirectional cylinders, during the transient part of the diffusion.

Figure 3: Multi-scale transverse stress states in the internal ply of the (a) $\pm 55^\circ$ laminate / (b) unidirectional composite structure.

The coupled model predicts transverse stresses states the absolute value of which is weaker than that predicted by the corresponding uncoupled approach. This result can be attributed to the weaker moisture content predicted by the coupled model compared to that deduced from the uncoupled approach, in the considered ply (Figure 2). Whatever the considered stacking of the plies, the most significant discrepancies between the transverse stresses predicted by the coupled/uncoupled models occur at the beginning of the diffusion process. In the organic matrix, the absolute deviation can be as strong as 20 MPa in the unidirectional structure. However, the discrepancy rapidly fades and cancels when the permanent state is attained in this structure. On the opposite, in the laminate, an absolute deviation of 10 MPa still holds in the permanent state of the diffusion process, regarding the predicted transverse stress experienced by the organic matrix. In any case, the strongest relative deviation occurring between the transverse stresses calculated through the coupled/uncoupled models corresponds to the transient

stage when the multi-scale stresses reach their extreme value, which is a deciding factor in the context of predicting the structure durability.

Figure 4 shows the comparison between the predicted in-plane shear stresses calculated in the internal ply of the laminated hollow cylinder.

Figure 4: Multi-scale shear stresses in the internal ply of the $\pm 55^\circ$ composite laminate.

It clearly appears on Figure 4, that, at the beginning of the diffusion process, (namely, between 50 and 500 days), the shear stresses predicted according to the coupled approach increase faster, in absolute value, than those deduced from the un-coupled model. This effect has been attributed to the strongest local moisture content gradients induced by the discontinuities (see Figure 2) in the case that the coupled model is used by comparison with the uncoupled model, for this specific period of time. In the following of the diffusion process, the absolute value of the stresses predicted by the coupled approach fall under the levels reached according to the uncoupled model. The behaviour is then similar to that described in the comments related to Figure 3.

CONCLUSIONS

A multi-scale approach accounting for a hygro-mechanical coupling was used in the present work in order to achieve the determination of the time and space dependent internal stresses resulting from the purely hygroscopic loading of thin composite laminates. The coupling involves considering an evolution of the moisture transport process parameters as a function of the volume strain of the organic matrix. The effective diffusion coefficient of the composite plies is estimated from the homogenization procedure established by Hashin. Accounting for the occurrence of the hygro-mechanical coupling yields a significant evolution of the moisture diffusion law governing parameters: the diffusion coefficient, and the maximum moisture absorption capacity, each of them varying through the depth of the composite structure, also. Moreover the choice of the geometrical stacking of the composite plies, since it enables to optimize the multi-scale mechanical states experienced by the composite structure, also enable to significantly optimize the parameters of the moisture diffusion process, so that the time and depth dependent moisture content profiles would be significantly weaker than the corresponding profile predicted in an unidirectional structure. Finally, the hygro-mechanical coupled model yields multi-scale mechanical stresses being

weaker than that predicted by the uncoupled model. Thus, accounting for the existence of the organic matrix volume strain effects on the moisture diffusion should be considered as a significant parameter as regard to the sizing of composite structures conceived for withstanding hygro-mechanical loads during their service-life.

In further works, the evolution, reported in practice [20], of the organic matrix mechanical stiffness, as a function of its moisture content, will be considered in the multi-scale coupled approach presented in this work. Since according to [21, this yields to the occurrence of an in-depth macroscopic properties evolution during the transient part of the diffusion process a dedicated, non iterative homogenization scale transition procedure based on Mori-Tanaka estimates [22] instead of the presently used Eshelby-Kröner model, would be required.

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